

Research Article

Current temperatures limit the potential impact of a commonly traded predatory gastropod

James W. E. Dickey^{1,2,3,4}, Jonathan M. Jeschke^{1,2,3}, Gregor T. Steffen⁴, Elžbieta Kazanavičiūtė^{4,5}, Reid S. Brennan⁴, Elizabeta Briski⁴

¹ Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries (IGB), Müggelseedamm 301, 12587 Berlin, Germany

² Freie Universität Berlin, Institute of Biology, Königin-Luise-Str. 1–3, 14195 Berlin, Germany

³ Berlin-Brandenburg Institute of Advanced Biodiversity Research, Königin-Luise-Str. 2–4, 14195 Berlin, Germany

⁴ GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel, Kiel, Germany

⁵ Lancaster University, Lancaster, LA1 4YW, UK

Corresponding author: James W. E. Dickey (jamesdickey03@gmail.com)

Academic editor: Ting Hui Ng

Received: 6 October 2022

Accepted: 29 December 2022

Published: 28 June 2023

Editors' Note: This is an additional contribution to the Proceedings of the 22nd International Conference on Aquatic Invasive Species held in Oostende, Belgium, April 18–22, 2022 (<https://icaais.org>). This conference has provided a venue for the exchange of information on various aspects of aquatic invasive species since its inception in 1990. The conference continues to provide an opportunity for dialog between academia, industry and environmental regulators.

Citation: Dickey JWE, Jeschke JM, Steffen GT, Kazanavičiūtė E, Brennan RS, Briski E (2023) Current temperatures limit the potential impact of a commonly traded predatory gastropod. *Aquatic Invasions* 18(2): 247–261. <https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2023.18.2.103208>

Copyright: © James W. E. Dickey et al. This is an open access article distributed under terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License ([Attribution 4.0 International – CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)).

Abstract

The pet trade has facilitated the spread of invasive alien species (IAS) globally, with negative consequences for biodiversity. The prediction of impacts is a major goal for invasion ecologists, and is especially crucial in an industry often lacking knowledge about traded species. We focused on the predatory gastropod *Anentome helena*, a species originating in south-east Asia and traded around the world, but with taxonomic uncertainty. We first set out to determine where our study organism fell within the *A. "helena"* species complex, known to comprise at least four cryptic species, before assessing the effect of temperature on the number of prey, the pulmonate snail *Physella acuta*, killed per predator via functional response experiments at two temperatures. We used 22 °C as a recommended temperature for housing the species in captivity, and 18 °C as a representative summer lake temperature in temperate climates of Europe. We also assessed the role of predator group size (1×, 2×, 3×) on predation (total consumption and average *per capita* consumption) at the experimental temperatures with fixed densities of prey, as well as the effect of these temperatures on prey activity. Our organisms belonged to a cryptic species originating from Thailand (*Anentome* sp. A), matching the findings of aquarium trade samples in other continents. In the functional response experiments, we found maximum feeding rate to be significantly reduced at the lower temperature. A similar result ensued from group feeding, with total consumption significantly reduced and the reduction in average *per capita* consumption approaching significance at the lower temperature. There was no significant effect of group size on the average *per capita* consumption in the group trial, indicating neutral conspecific interactions. No significant effect of temperature on the activity of the prey species was found, suggesting decreased consumption was mainly driven by predator, rather than prey. These results suggest limited *A. helena* impacts in the short-term, but increasing temperatures with climate change may facilitate greater consequences from releases. We suggest future studies assess other potential predatory impacts and survival across relevant abiotic conditions, and encourage the use of similar methods to assess the impacts of other commonly traded species.

Key words: *Anentome helena*, ecological impact, functional response, invasive alien species, molecular identification, pet trade

Introduction

The unrelenting spread of invasive alien species (IAS) is one of the major drivers of global biodiversity loss (Seebens et al. 2017; IPBES 2019). An increasingly globalised world has led to new pathways facilitating this movement of species, and the pet trade is one important driver of this development (Lockwood et al. 2019). While many species within the pet trade spend their entire lives in confinement, the risk of escape or release from producers, importers, retailers and owners is ever-present. Indeed, the pet trade has facilitated the establishment of non-native populations globally, and is deemed responsible for 53% of invasive vertebrate species (Saul et al. 2017; Gippet and Bertelsmeier 2021) and a third of all aquatic IAS (Padilla and Williams 2004), with escapes and releases by aquarists a major contributor of invasive freshwater species in Europe (Nunes et al. 2015). The industry is also known to be poorly regulated (Raghavan et al. 2013), with species often only identified to their genus names, or worse, misidentified (Shivambu et al. 2020b).

Molluscs, primarily gastropods and bivalves, are popular within the pet trade globally (Ng et al. 2016b; Banha et al. 2019; Shivambu et al. 2020a), for both ornamental appeal and algae control (Patoka et al. 2017). Releases have led to a number of high-profile mollusc IAS emerging from the pet trade with negative ecological impacts. For example, the South American golden apple snail (*Pomacea canaliculata* Lamarck, 1822) has established non-native populations in the United States, Japan, China, Taiwan, Thailand and Indonesia (Shivambu et al. 2020a), and is believed to have reduced native freshwater snail populations, become an agricultural pest, and acted as a host for parasites (Halwart 1994; Rawlings et al. 2007). Aquarium releases have also seen *Melanooides tuberculata* (O. F. Müller, 1774), a species with a broad African and Asian native range, and the south-east Asian *Tarebia granifera* (Lamarck, 1816) establish extensive invasion histories (Rader et al. 2003; Raw et al. 2015; Da Silva et al. 2019; Makherana et al. 2022), posing threats to native biodiversity. While the majority of gastropods in the pet trade are thought to be herbivorous or detritivorous, the “assassin snail” *Anentome helena* (von dem Busch, 1847; formerly *Clea helena*) is readily available (Patoka et al. 2017; Shivambu et al. 2020a) and in possession of carnivorous habits. Uncertainty surrounds its taxonomic identity, with *A. helena* thought to comprise a cryptic complex of at least four species (*Anentome “helena”*: Strong et al. 2017), however a sample from the US pet trade was found to be conspecific with those already established in Singapore, a global ornamental pet trading hub, which may indicate ubiquity of this species in the trade (Ng et al. 2016a; Strong et al. 2017). With concern over further non-native establishment elsewhere (Bogan and Hanneman 2013), its potential to exert impacts in ecosystems beyond its native range is in need of study.

With *A. helena* found to be amongst the most readily available aquatic gastropods in Germany (Dickey et al. in prep), we aimed to solve the taxonomic uncertainty by phylogenetically analysing our study organisms, and then by assessing the role of temperature on its potential predatory impact. While availability has been shown to be a suitable proxy for propagule pressure (Duggan et al. 2006; Chucholl 2013), abiotic barriers to growth and survival must be overcome (Blackburn et al. 2011), and abiotic tolerances, especially to low temperatures, have proven crucial to the establishment success of numerous pet trade species (Vesely et al. 2015; Standfuss et al. 2016). Therefore, we set out to assess how temperature affects the feeding rates of *A. helena* on *Physella acuta* (Draparnaud, 1805) prey, a wide-ranging aquatic

pulmonate snail present in Europe since the 1700s (Vinarski 2017). We used two experimental temperatures: 22 °C, a recommended lower limit for keeping the species in home aquaria (e.g. Aquariumtips.org 2020; Interaquaristik.de 2022; Tierlexikon.info 2022), and 18 °C, a temperature representative of summer water temperatures in temperate climates such as in Europe. We tested *per capita* feeding rates under these temperature treatments using functional response experiments (i.e. measures of how prey consumption varies with prey density), which have been used effectively as a means of assessing the impacts of invasive species over the past decade due to their ability to incorporate a wealth of context dependencies (Dick et al. 2014, 2017). However, one potential limitation of this measure of *per capita* consumption is that it typically does not account for the role of conspecific interactions inherent in group foraging, something potentially important in the context of pet species releases, when small numbers of individuals might be released together. There are three broad categories of conspecific interactions: neutral, antagonistic (prey risk reducing: Livernois et al. 2019), and synergistic (prey risk enhancing: Livernois et al. 2019), and using different experimental predator densities (i.e. fixed prey densities with single, double and triple predators), we assessed how temperature affects group feeding rates. We also assessed the role of temperature on the activity levels of *P. acuta* in order to elucidate whether predator or prey were the primary drivers of any differences in consumption at the two experimental temperatures. In summary, our study objectives were to 1) determine where our *A. helena* study organisms fell within the *Anentome* “*helena*” species complex; and test: 2) whether temperature would affect *per capita* consumption of *A. helena* using functional response experiments, 3) whether temperature and/or group size would affect feeding rates (total consumption and average *per capita* consumption) using our group feeding tests, and 4) whether our experimental temperatures would affect the activity levels of the prey species, *P. acuta*.

Methods

Anentome helena (Figure 1) were ordered online (garnelen-direkt.de) and arrived on 15th March 2022. The snails were held in an 18 °C lab with an 8-hour light regime for five days in a 56 L glass tank (i.e. 60 cm × 30 cm × 30 cm length, width and height) containing a 1 cm-deep layer of sand, and a heater (Eheim, Germany) and probe (Aqua-medic Titanium, Germany) to maintain the water temperature at 22 °C. *Anentome helena* were held under these conditions for five days before being split into two groups, i.e. a “warm” group and a “cold” group. On day six, the temperature of the “cold” group was dropped to 20 °C, and further to 18 °C on day seven. Temperature was adjusted via thermostat, so no additional disturbance of the snails in the “cold” group occurred. Snails in both groups were fed once every three days with frozen mysids (Petman Premium, Germany). The prey species, *P. acuta* (Figure 2), were ordered from Shrimpfarm-Frankfurt.de and arrived on 10th March. They were held in a covered plastic aquaria (approx. 50 *P. acuta* per 2 L, 18 cm × 12 cm × 12 cm) with an air stone and wooden sticks for habitat complexity, and fed “Veggie Wafers” food pellets (Tetra, U.S.A.) every three days. They were held in the same 18 °C lab as *A. helena*.

Molecular identification of *A. helena*

DNA was extracted from the foot tissue of ten snail specimens using the DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (Qiagen, Germany) following the manufacturer’s instructions. A fragment of the mitochondrial cytochrome *c* oxidase subunit I (*COI*)

Figure 1. Photographs of predator *A. helena*. Morphological similarity noted between our study individuals and *Anentome* sp. A in the *A. "helena"* complex (Strong et al. 2017).

Figure 2. Photographs of prey *P. acuta* specimens (a–d) with a demonstration of relative size between the predator, left, and prey (d).

was amplified using primer pair LCO1490 (5'-GGTCAACAAATCATAAAGATATTGG-3') and HCO2198 (5'-TAAACTTCAGGGTGACCAAAAAATCA-3') (Folmer et al. 1994). PCR reactions were conducted in 10 μ L volume reactions,

containing 1 μL of forward and reverse primers (5 mM concentration), template DNA, 10X PCR buffer (Invitrogen, USA) and dNTPs, 0.1 μL Taq DNA Polymerase (Invitrogen, USA) and 4.9 μL of nuclease-free water. Amplification was performed under the following conditions: 94 °C for 3 minutes; 35 cycles of 94 °C for 45 seconds, 48 °C for 45 seconds, and 72 °C for 60 seconds; 72 °C for 7 minutes. Consequently, we obtained quality PCR product for one specimen. PCR product was sequenced on Sanger sequencing platform (Applied Biosystems, USA) at Eurofins Genomics (Kiel, Germany).

Raw forward and reverse sequences were assembled in CodonCode Aligner (v 3.7.1; Codon Code Corporation). *Anentome "helena"* consists of multiple, undescribed, cryptic species (Strong et al. 2017). To validate the species identification, we conducted a phylogenetic analysis using known samples representing the four cryptic species as well as the closely related *Nassodonta dorri* (Wattebled, 1886), with *Naytia granulosa* (Lamarck, 1822) as an outgroup; these samples were downloaded from NCBI (Suppl. material 1: table S1). Samples were aligned using MUSCLE v3.8.1551 (Edgar 2004). A maximum likelihood tree was constructed using MEGA v 10.2.6 with 1000 bootstrap replicates.

Functional response trials

Prior to trials commencing, snails from both groups were removed from the holding tanks and starved for 48 hours in 1 L of water within 2 L plastic aquaria (18 cm \times 12 cm \times 12 cm) containing a 1 cm depth of sand, an air line and covered with a plastic sheet, and held within the respective "warm" and "cold" water baths (77 L plastic container: 70 cm \times 55 cm \times 20 cm) containing a heater, probe and two circulation pumps (Tunze, Germany) to ensure even distribution of temperature (see Suppl. material 1: figure S1 for experimental set up). *Physella acuta* prey were sorted and given a 24-hour adaptation to the experimental conditions, also in 2 L aquaria with an air line and covered, and held in the baths. Experimental arenas (1 L plastic jars: 9 cm \times 9 cm \times 14 cm) were filled with 400 ml of water and added to the water baths 24 hours before trials began in order to give sufficient time for them to reach the desired experimental temperatures. During this time, and during the experimental trials, air lines were in the water to remove any potential confounding factors arising from warmer water holding less oxygen. On the day of the trials, the experimental prey densities (1, 2, 4, 8 and 16; $n = 4$ per prey density per temperature treatment) were sorted and added to the arenas 30 minutes before *A. helena*. Trials commenced upon the addition of a single predator to the arena and loosely closing the arena lid. Control trials ($n = 4$ per prey density per temperature treatment) involved the same preparation only without the addition of a predator to quantify *P. acuta* mortality for any other reason. Trials ran for 48 hours, after which they were ended by the removal of each arena's *A. helena*. The number of live *P. acuta* was subsequently counted to determine predator consumption.

Group feeding trials

After the commencement of functional response experiments, *A. helena* were returned to holding tanks with conspecifics and left undisturbed for 7 days. 24 "warm" and 24 "cold" *A. helena* were then selected haphazardly for group feeding trials and starved for 48 hours in covered, aerated 2 L aquaria (density of 12 snails per tank). 480 *P. acuta* were selected from holding tanks 24 hours before trials commenced and split into a "warm" group and a "cold" group, also held in covered, aerated 2 L aquaria. On the day of the trials, *P. acuta* were grouped into

densities of 20 before addition to the experimental arenas (1 L plastic jars with 400 ml water as in functional response trials), 30 minutes before the addition of *A. helena*. Trials commenced upon the addition of *A. helena*, which were added to experimental trials in groups of 1, 2 or 3 ($n = 5$ per density), and the closing of the arena lid. Again, trials ran for 48 hours and the water was oxygenated throughout the trials to prevent any confounds from temperature or from snail density.

Physella acuta activity

To assess the effect of the two trial temperatures on the *P. acuta* prey, we measured activity in 100 ml water in round plastic dishes (dimensions: diameter 8.4 cm, height 4.2 cm). Each dish had a cross drawn across on the base, and activity was recorded using a CX action camera (ACTIVEON Inc., U.S.A.). Videos were watched back, with the number of line-crosses over a 20-minute experimental period counting as an indicator of activity. The experimental period began ten seconds after the final *P. acuta* per batch of four was added to its dish. The sample size was $n = 16$ per temperature treatment.

Data analyses

All analyses took place in R version 4.1.2 (2021-11-01). Functional responses were modelled using the “fRair” package (Pritchard et al. 2017), with the type of curve (i.e. linear Type I, hyperbolic Type II or sigmoidal Type III) derived through logistic regression considering the proportion of prey consumed as a function of initial prey density, with a significantly negative first-order term indicative of a Type II, and a significantly positive first-order term followed by a significantly negative second-order term indicative of a Type III. Functional responses of each species at each salinity were modelled using maximum likelihood estimation (MLE; Bolker et al. 2009) and the random predator equation (Rogers 1972), due to prey not being replaced as they were consumed:

$$N_c = N_0(1 - \exp(a(N_c h - T))) \quad (1)$$

where N_c is the number of prey consumed, N_0 is the initial density of prey, a is the attack rate, h is the handling time and T is the total time available (i.e. 48 hours). Models were fitted to the data using the Lambert W function owing to the recursive nature of the random predator equation (Bolker 2008). The initial a and h estimates were non-parametrically bootstrapped ($n = 2000$) to construct 95% confidence intervals around the functional response curve for each treatment. Significant differences between attack rates and handling times can be determined by visual inspection of confidence intervals (Figure 4), or using the delta or difference method of Juliano (2001) (Suppl. material 1: table S3; see Pritchard et al. 2017).

In the group feeding trials, the effect of temperature and predator density on 1) total consumption and 2) average *per capita* consumption (i.e. total consumption divided by the predator density) were assessed using generalised linear models. For 1) a Quasipoisson distribution was used due to overdispersion, and for 2) a Gaussian distribution. In each model, backward eliminations of non-significant terms and interactions resulted in the most parsimonious fits (Crawley 2014). Post-hoc tests with Tukey p value adjustment were performed using the emmeans package (Lenth et al. 2020) to assess differences in total consumption between combinations of temperature and group size.

For the test of *P. acuta* activity, the effect of temperature on activity (i.e. the number of line crosses) was assessed using a generalised linear model with Quasi-poisson distribution.

Results

Molecular identification of *A. helena*

Phylogenetic analysis showed that our specimen belonged to *Anentome* sp. A, as determined in Strong et al. (2017) (Figure 3). This species originates from Thailand and other samples purchased through the aquarium trade in the USA have belonged to this clade (Strong et al. 2017). This suggests that aquarium animals from the USA and Europe are from a common source. Analysis using a neighbour-joining approach, not shown, produced the same results.

Figure 3. Maximum likelihood tree based on the mitochondrial gene COI. Bootstrap support values are shown at nodes and the scale bar represents the number of nucleotide substitutions per site. The sample used in this experiment, “Our Sample”, falls with *Anentome* sp. A. See Suppl. material 1: table S1 for sample information.

Functional response trials

Prey survival in all controls was 100%, and therefore all prey mortality was attributed to *A. helena* consumption. Type II functional responses were observed under both temperature treatments, as determined by significantly negative first-order terms (Suppl. material 1: table S2, Figure 4). There was a significantly greater value for the handling time parameter at 18 °C ($p < 0.05$; Suppl. material 1: table S3), and hence, a lower maximum feeding rate (i.e. $1/b$) than at 22 °C (22 °C: 4.264 consumed; 18 °C: 1.036 consumed).

Figure 4. Functional Responses of *Anentome helena* towards *Physella acuta* prey at 22 °C and 18 °C temperature treatments. Experimental trials lasted 48 hours. Shaded areas are bootstrapped 95% confidence intervals.

Group feeding trials

There was a significant effect of temperature and group size on total consumption (adjusted $R^2 = 0.937$, $F_{3,26} = 144$, $p < 0.001$; Figure 5), but the two-way interaction was non-significant. Consumption at 18 °C was significantly less than at 22 °C (mean difference \pm SE = -0.811 ± 0.321 , $F_{1,26} = 6.551$, $p = 0.018$), consumption for groups of three was significantly greater than for single predators (mean difference \pm SE = 1.308 ± 0.446 , $t = 1.909$, $p < 0.01$), with the difference in consumption between groups of two and single predators approaching significance (0.896 ± 0.469 , $t = 1.909$, $p = 0.067$). Post-hoc comparisons revealed significant differences in consumption between temperature-group size treatments (Suppl. material 1: table S4). When the effects of temperature and group size on *per capita* consumption were assessed, there was an effect approaching significance for temperature ($p = 0.054$), but no significant effect of group size ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 5. Total consumption (a) and average *per capita* consumption (b) of *Anentome helena* across three predator group size treatments towards *Physella acuta* at 22 °C (red) and 18 °C (blue) temperature treatments. Trials lasted 48 hours.

Physella acuta activity

Though higher at 22 °C, there was no significant effect of temperature on *P. acuta* activity (mean \pm 95% CI: 22 °C, 7.50 \pm 3.889; 18 °C, 4.75 \pm 1.810; $p = 0.164$).

Discussion

The international pet trade is highly diverse, but knowledge gaps exist for many of the species sold, both in terms of taxonomic identification and the potential ecological impacts they might have if released. Temperature remains a crucial barrier to IAS establishment, proliferation and impact (Rahel and Olden 2008; Standfuss et al. 2016; Hesselschwerdt and Wantzen 2018), and with the risk of pet releases or escapes ever-present, there remains a need to establish its effect on the potential impacts of commonly traded species. Here, we show that a readily available mollusc in the German pet trade, *A. helena*, or *Anentome* sp. A (Strong et al. 2017), is capable of surviving and feeding at an ecologically relevant temperature lower than typically recommended for the species, but with reduced predatory capacity.

Functional responses, and maximum feeding rates in particular, have been used effectively as ways of quantifying the ecological impacts of invasive species across abiotic contexts (Dick et al. 2014; Dickey et al. 2021). Here, we demonstrated that at the 18 °C temperature treatment there was a significantly reduced maximum feeding rate relative to the 22 °C treatment for *A. helena* on *P. acuta* prey. The functional response method is ultimately a *per capita* measure of impact, however, and while a valuable and popular impact assessment method, it may give a reduced or enhanced consumption rate by often failing to account for interactions between conspecifics. Indeed, conspecific interactions, both synergistic and agonistic, have been shown to facilitate invasive species success. For example, aggression towards conspecifics is thought to facilitate spread (e.g. aggressive individuals inhabiting the range frontier: Groen et al. 2012), while a lack of aggression towards conspecifics may facilitate coexistence in high densities in the invaded range (e.g. Argentine ant, *Linepithema humile* Mayr, 1868: Suarez et al. 1999; Asian shore crab, *Hemigrapsus sanguineus* De Haan, 1835: Hobbs et al. 2017). Further, simply the presence of conspecifics in feeding trials may limit stress and give more representative feeding rates. We therefore incorporated group feeding trials into our study, with different predator densities (i.e. foraging group sizes) and fixed prey densities in order to assess the role of temperature and group size on the total feeding rates and average *per capita* feeding rates (defined as total consumption divided by group size). For the latter measure, we propose that consistent feeding rates across group sizes would indicate neutral interactions, whereas increasing would be indicative of synergistic interactions and decreasing indicative of agonistic interactions. In our trials, temperature and group size were shown to significantly affect total consumption, however, there was a lack of significant two-way interaction, indicating that group size played the same role on consumption rates at both temperatures. While there was an effect approaching significance of temperature on average *per capita* feeding in the group trial, the lack of predator density effect suggests neutral rather than synergistic (for example, coordinated group hunting) or agonistic group feeding effects (such as interference competition).

While not significant between the two temperature treatments, prey activity levels were higher at 22 °C, which could potentially have increased the encounter rate and in turn led to a higher attack rate, but this turned out not to be the case, with no significant difference in attack rates between the two treatments. However, maximum feeding rates were significantly different, and this may have been driven by the predator's metabolism and digestion (Jeschke et al. 2002; Brown et al. 2004;

but see Marshall and McQuaid 2011) or handling time. Hunting by *A. helena* involves subduing prey with their foot, and then consuming it via its aperture (Berkhout and Morozov 2022). It may be that hunting or digesting prey became more difficult, or more protracted processes at the colder treatment. Considering the 48-hour experiment time, digestion may have had the stronger influence on observed consumption, thus the observed differences are probably due to a longer digestion time at the colder treatment. This may have long-term implications for survival of the species at more stressful temperatures. We recommend future studies to assess the role of temperature on alternative, less energetically costly food resources, such as less motile or less protected prey, or on carrion which they are also known to feed upon (Bogan and Hanneman 2013). Indeed, a switch from hunter to scavenger at lower temperatures may facilitate survival. Studies assessing the role of various abiotic stressors on *A. helena* mortality would prove useful too (e.g. Paiva et al. 2020; Cuthbert et al. 2021), such as lower temperatures, differing dissolved oxygen levels and salinity levels representative of estuarine conditions or urban ponds (Van Meter et al. 2011). Further, as a dioecious gastropod (Coelho et al. 2013), unlike invasive species exhibiting parthenogenesis such as *M. tuberculata* (Brandt et al. 1996) and *Tarebia granifera* (Miranda et al. 2011), the presence of both sexes is crucial to the establishment of wild populations. How such abiotic conditions affect reproduction and whether there are survival differences between sexes require further study.

In the short term, it appears likely that the areas most at risk from *A. helena* are thermally influenced freshwater systems, of which there are many in Europe. The Rhine, the Weser and the Po watersheds have all been shown to have a large proportion of their flows affected by thermal pollution during the year (Raptis et al. 2016). The Gillbach-Erft river system in Germany, for example, with temperatures rarely falling below 19 °C, became the home of numerous tropical and subtropical fish, crustaceans and molluscs (Emde et al. 2016; Jourdan et al. 2017; Lukas et al. 2017), and thermal pools in Hungary have also seen the establishment of diverse, non-native crayfish assemblages (Weiperth et al. 2020). Further, climate change as well as expanding urban areas with heat island effects – deemed “gateways to new ranges” (Borden and Flory 2021) – are of particular note considering that this is where most pet trade releases occur. Further research is required focused on how such habitats might host populations capable of undergoing inherent or prolonged lags (Crooks 2005), or “sleeping populations” waiting for a trigger to become abundant and disruptive (Spear et al. 2021), and facilitate adaptation and spread to colder conditions. Going forward, we propose that combining the monitoring of pet stores, garden centres, websites and online marketplaces (Ng et al. 2016b; Shivambu et al. 2020a, 2020b; Olden et al. 2021), with methods to assess the potential impacts of the species sold (Dickey et al. 2022) and their “hitchhikers” (Stanicka et al. 2022), will prove increasingly crucial in helping to determine the next potential invaders.

Funding declaration

JWED was supported by the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation.

Author's contribution

JWED, MJM and EB conceived the study. JWED performed the experiments, with valuable assistance from GTS, and performed statistical analysis and prepared the initial manuscript. EK conducted molecular laboratory work, while RSB processed the molecular data. All authors provided valuable input to the development of the final manuscript and have given approval for publication.

Data availability

Sequence data used for species identification is available on NCBI accession number [OQ075971](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuclseq/OQ075971). Accessions for all samples used in this study can be found in Suppl. material 1: table S1.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to acknowledge the thematic editor Ian Duggan and two anonymous reviewers for their thorough and constructive comments during the review process which undoubtedly helped improve the quality of the manuscript.

References

- Aquariumtips.org (2020) Snail Helena. [aquariumtips.org. https://aquariumtips.org/other-species/marine-invertebrates/snail-helena/](https://aquariumtips.org/other-species/marine-invertebrates/snail-helena/) [August 10, 2022]
- Banha F, Diniz A, Anastácio PM (2019) Patterns and drivers of aquarium pet discharge in the wild. *Ecological Indicators* 106: 105513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2019.105513>
- Berkhout BW, Morozov A (2022) Assassin snails (*Anentome helena*) as a biological model for exploring the effects of individual specialisation within generalist predators. *PLoS ONE* 17: 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0264996>
- Blackburn TM, Pyšek P, Bacher S, Carlton JT, Duncan RP, Jarošík V, Wilson JR, Richardson DM (2011) A proposed unified framework for biological invasions. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution* 26: 333–339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2011.03.023>
- Bogan A, Hanneman EH (2013) A carnivorous aquatic gastropod in the pet trade in North America: The next threat to freshwater gastropods. *Ellipsaria* 15: 18–19.
- Bolker B (2008) *Ecological models and data in R*. Princeton University Press, Princeton.
- Bolker BM, Brooks ME, Clark CJ, Geange SW, Poulsen JR, Stevens MHH, White JSS (2009) Generalized linear mixed models: a practical guide for ecology and evolution. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution* 24: 127–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2008.10.008>
- Borden JB, Flory SL (2021) Urban evolution of invasive species. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 19(3): 184–191. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.2295>
- Brande S, Turner M, Heller J, Ben-Yehuda OZ (1996) Statistical discrimination of sex in *Melanooides tuberculata* (Gastropoda: Thiaridae). *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* 59: 87–112. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-8312.1996.tb01454.x>
- Brown JH, Gillooly JF, Allen AP, Savage VM, West GB (2004) Toward a Metabolic Theory of Ecology. *Ecology* 7: 1771–1789. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-820581-5.00016-X>
- Churchill C (2013) Invaders for sale: Trade and determinants of introduction of ornamental freshwater crayfish. *Biological Invasions* 15: 125–141. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-012-0273-2>
- Coelho AR, Dinis MT, Reis J (2013) Effect of diet and stocking densities on life history traits of *Clea helena* (Philippi 1847) reared in captivity. *Journal of Aquaculture Research and Development* 4(5): 1000187. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2155-9546.1000187>
- Crawley (2013) *The R Book*. 2nd edn. John Wiley & Sons, Chichester, 551–659.
- Crooks JA (2005) Lag times and exotic species: The ecology and management of biological invasions in slow-motion. *Ecoscience* 12: 316–329. <https://doi.org/10.2980/i1195-6860-12-3-316.1>
- Cuthbert RN, Sidow A, Frost KE, Kotronaki SG, Briski E (2021) Emergent effects of temperature and salinity on mortality of a key herbivore. *Journal of Sea Research* 177: 102126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seares.2021.102126>
- Da Silva EL, Leal MF, Santos O Dos, Da Rocha AJ, Pacheco ACL, Pinheiro TG (2019) New records of the invasive mollusk *Melanooides tuberculata* (Müller, 1774) (Gastropoda, Thiaridae) in the Brazilian Northeast. *Check List* 15: 479–483. <https://doi.org/10.15560/15.3.479>

- Dick JTA, Alexander ME, Jeschke JM, Ricciardi A, MacIsaac HJ, Robinson TB, Kumschick S, Weyl OLF, Dunn AM, Hatcher MJ, Paterson RA, Farnsworth KD, Richardson DM (2014) Advancing impact prediction and hypothesis testing in invasion ecology using a comparative functional response approach. *Biological Invasions* 16: 735–753. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-013-0550-8>
- Dick JTA, Alexander ME, Ricciardi A, Laverty C, Paul OD, Xu M, Jeschke JM, Saul W, Hill MP, Neill DB-O, Weyl OLF, Shaw RH (2017) Functional responses can unify invasion ecology. *Biological Invasions* 19: 1667–1672. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-016-1355-3>
- Dickey JWE, Cuthbert RN, Steffen GT, Dick JTA, Briski E (2021) Sea freshening may drive the ecological impacts of emerging and existing invasive non-native species. *Diversity and Distributions* 27: 144–156. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.13178>
- Dickey JWE, Arnott G, McGlade CLO, Moore A, Riddell GE, Dick JTA (2022) Threats at home? Assessing the potential ecological impacts and risks of commonly traded pet fishes. *NeoBiota* 73: 109–136. <https://doi.org/10.3897/neobiota.73.80542>
- Duggan IC, Rixon CAM, Macisaac HJ (2006) Popularity and propagule pressure: determinants of introduction and establishment of aquarium fish. *Biological Invasions* 8: 377–382. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-004-2310-2>
- Edgar RC (2004) MUSCLE: Multiple Sequence Alignment with High Accuracy and High Throughput. *Nucleic Acids Research* 32: 1792–1797. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkh340>
- Emde S, Kochmann J, Kuhn T, Dörge DD, Plath M, Miesen FW, Klimpel S (2016) Cooling water of power plant creates “hot spots” for tropical fishes and parasites. *Parasitology Research* 115: 85–98. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-015-4724-4>
- Folmer O, Black M, Hoeh W, Lutz R, Vrijenhoek R (1994) DNA primers for amplification of mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I from diverse metazoan invertebrates. *Molecular Marine Biology and Biotechnology* 3(5): 294–299.
- Gippet JMW, Bertelsmeier C (2021) Invasiveness is linked to greater commercial success in the global pet trade. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Science USA* 118(14): e2016337118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2016337118>
- Halwart M (1994) The golden apple snail *Pomacea canaliculata* in asian rice farming systems: Present impact and future threat. *International Journal of Pest Management* 40: 199–206. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09670879409371882>
- Hesselschwerdt J, Wantzen KM (2018) Global warming may lower thermal barriers against invasive species in freshwater ecosystems – A study from Lake Constance. *Science of the Total Environment* 645: 44–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.07.078>
- Hobbs NVS, Cobb JS, Thornber CS (2017) Conspecific tolerance and heterospecific competition as mechanisms for overcoming resistance to invasion by an intertidal crab. *Biological Invasions* 19: 765–772. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-016-1290-3>
- Interaquaristik.de (2022) Raubturmdeckelschnecke, *Anentome helena*. <https://www.interaquaristik.de/tiere/schnecken/raubturmdeckelschnecke-anentome-helena/a-9721>
- IPBES (2019) Summary for policymakers of the global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services. Bonn, Germany, 39 pp.
- Jeschke JM, Kopp M, Tollrian R (2002) Predator functional responses: Discriminating between handling and digesting prey. *Ecological Monographs* 72: 95–112. [https://doi.org/10.1890/0012-9615\(2002\)072\[0095:PFRDBH\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/0012-9615(2002)072[0095:PFRDBH]2.0.CO;2)
- Livernois MC, Fodrie FJ, Heck KL, Powers SP (2019) Emergent intraspecific multiple predator effects shape estuarine trophic dynamics across a gradient of habitat complexity. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 511: 120–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2018.12.004>
- Lockwood JL, Welbourne DJ, Romagosa CM, Cassey P, Mandrak NE, Strecker A, Leung B, Stringham OC, Udell B, Episcopo-Sturgeon DJ, Tlusty MF, Sinclair J, Springborn MR, Pienaar EF, Rhyne AL, Keller R (2019) When pets become pests: the role of the exotic pet trade in producing invasive vertebrate animals. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 17: 323–330. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fec.2059>

- Lukas JAY, Jourdan J, Kalinkat G, Emde S, Miesen FW, Jungling H, Cocchiararo B, Bierbach D (2017) On the occurrence of three non-native cichlid species including the first record of a feral population of *Pelmatolapia (Tilapia) mariae* (Boulenger, 1899) in Europe. Royal Society Open Science 4: 170160. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.170160>
- Makherana F, Cuthbert RN, Dondofema F, Wasserman RJ, Chauke GM, Munyai LF, Dalu T (2022) Distribution, drivers and population structure of the invasive alien snail *Tarebia granifera* in the Luvuvhu system, South Africa. River Research and Applications 38(8): 1362–1373. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rra.3937>
- Marshall DJ, McQuaid CD (2011) Warming reduces metabolic rate in marine snails: Adaptation to fluctuating high temperatures challenges the metabolic theory of ecology. Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences 278: 281–288. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2010.1414>
- Miranda NAF, Perissinotto R, Appleton CC (2011) Population Structure of an Invasive Parthenogenetic Gastropod in Coastal Lakes and Estuaries of Northern KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. PLoS ONE 6: e24337. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0024337>
- Ng TH, Foon JK, Tan SK, Chan MKK, Yeo DCJ (2016a) First non-native establishment of the carnivorous assassin snail, *Anentome helena* (von dem Busch in Philippi, 1847). BioInvasions Records 5(3): 143–148. <https://doi.org/10.3391/bir.2016.5.3.04>
- Ng TH, Tan SK, Wong WH, Meier R, Chan SY, Tan HH, Yeo DCJ (2016b) Molluscs for sale: Assessment of freshwater gastropods and bivalves in the ornamental pet trade. PLoS ONE 11: 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0161130>
- Nunes AL, Tricarico E, Panov VE, Cardoso AC, Katsanevakis S (2015) Pathways and gateways of freshwater invasions in Europe. Aquatic Invasions 10: 359–370. <https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2015.10.4.01>
- Olden JD, Whattam E, Wood SA (2021) Online auction marketplaces as a global pathway for aquatic invasive species. Hydrobiologia 848: 1967–1979. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-020-04407-7>
- Padilla DK, Williams SL (2004) Beyond ballast water: Aquarium and ornamental trades as sources of invasive species in aquatic ecosystems. Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment 2: 131–138. [https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295\(2004\)002\[0131:BBWAAO\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295(2004)002[0131:BBWAAO]2.0.CO;2)
- Paiva F, Pauli NC, Briski E (2020) Are juveniles as tolerant to salinity stress as adults? A case study of Northern European, Ponto-Caspian and North American species. Diversity and Distributions 26: 1627–1641. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.13147>
- Patoka J, Kopecký O, Vrabec V, Kalous L (2017) Aquarium molluscs as a case study in risk assessment of incidental freshwater fauna. Biological Invasions 19: 2039–2046. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-017-1412-6>
- Pritchard DW, Paterson RA, Bovy HC, Barrios-O'Neill D (2017) frair: an R package for fitting and comparing consumer functional responses. Methods in Ecology and Evolution 8: 1528–1534. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12784>
- Rader RB, Belk MC, Keleher MJ (2003) The Introduction of an Invasive Snail (*Melanoides tuberculata*) to Spring Ecosystems of the Bonneville Basin, Utah. Journal of Freshwater Ecology 18: 647–657. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02705060.2003.9664007>
- Raghavan R, Dahanukar N, Tlustý MF, Rhyne AL, Krishna Kumar K, Molur S, Rosser AM (2013) Uncovering an obscure trade: Threatened freshwater fishes and the aquarium pet markets. Biological Conservation 164: 158–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2013.04.019>
- Rahel FJ, Olden JD (2008) Assessing the effects of climate change on aquatic invasive species. Conservation Biology 22: 521–533. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2008.00950.x>
- Raptis CE, Van Vliet MTH, Pfister S (2016) Global thermal pollution of rivers from thermoelectric power plants. Environmental Research Letters 11: 104011. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/11/10/104011>
- Raw JL, Miranda NAF, Perissinotto R (2015) Chemical cues released by heterospecific competitors: behavioural responses of native and alien invasive aquatic gastropods. Aquatic Sciences 77: 655–666. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00027-015-0409-4>

- Rawlings TA, Hayes KA, Cowie RH, Collins TM (2007) The identity, distribution, and impacts of non-native apple snails in the continental United States. *BMC Evolutionary Biology* 7: 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2148-7-97>
- Rogers D (1972) Random Search and Insect Population Models. *Journal of Animal Ecology* 41: 369–383. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3474>
- Saul WC, Roy HE, Booy O, Carnevali L, Chen HJ, Genovesi P, Harrower CA, Hulme PE, Pagad S, Pergl J, Jeschke JM (2017) Assessing patterns in introduction pathways of alien species by linking major invasion data bases. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 54: 657–669. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12819>
- Seebens H, Blackburn TM, Dyer E, Genovesi P, Hulme PE, Jeschke JM, Pagad S, Pyšek P, Winter M, Arianoutsou M, Bacher S, Blasius B, Brundu G, Capinha C, Celesti-Grapow L, Dawson W, Dullinger S, Fuentes N, Jäger H, Kartesz J, Kenis M, Kreft H, Kühn I, Lenzner B, Liebhold A, Mosena A, Moser D, Nishino M, Pearman D, Pergl J, Rabitsch W, Rojas-Sandoval J, Roques A, Rorke S, Rossinelli S, Roy HE, Scalera R, Schindler S, Štajerová K, Tokarska-Guzik B, Kleunen M van, Walker K, Weigelt P, Yamanaka T, Essl F (2017) No saturation in the accumulation of alien species worldwide. *Nature Communications* 8: 14435. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms14435>
- Shivambu TC, Shivambu N, Downs CT (2020a) Exotic gastropods for sale: An assessment of land and aquatic snails in the south african pet trade. *Management of Biological Invasions* 11: 512–524. <https://doi.org/10.3391/mbi.2020.11.3.11>
- Shivambu TC, Shivambu N, Lyle R, Jacobs A, Kumschick S, Foord SH, Robertson MP (2020b) Tarantulas (Araneae: Theraphosidae) in the Pet Trade in South Africa. *African Zoology* 55(4): 323–336. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15627020.2020.1823879>
- Spear MJ, Walsh JR, Ricciardi A, Vander Zanden MJ (2021) The invasion ecology of sleeper populations: Prevalence, persistence, and abrupt shifts. *BioScience* 71(4): 357–369. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biaa168>
- Standfuss B, Lipovšek G, Fritz U, Vamberger M (2016) Threat or fiction: is the pond slider (*Trachemys scripta*) really invasive in Central Europe? A case study from Slovenia. *Conservation Genetics* 17: 557–563. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10592-015-0805-2>
- Stanicka A, Maciaszek R, Cichy A, Templin J, Świderek W, Żbikowska E, Labecka AM (2022) Unwanted ‘hitchhikers’ of ornamental snails: A case report of digeneans transported via the international pet trade. *The European Zoological Journal* 89: 601–607. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24750263.2022.2065039>
- Strong EE, Galindo LA, Kantor YI (2017) Quid est *Clea helena*? Evidence for a previously unrecognized radiation of assassin snails (Gastropoda: Buccinoidea: Nassariidae). *PeerJ* 2017: 1–41. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.3638>
- Tierlexikon.info (2022) *Clea helena* (Haltung). tierlexikon.info. <https://tierlexikon.info/clea-helena-haltung/> [August 10, 2022]
- Vesely L, Buřič M, Kouba A (2015) Hardy exotics species in temperate zone: can “warm water” crayfish invaders establish regardless of low temperatures? *Scientific Reports* 5: 16340. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep16340>
- Van Meter RJ, Swan CM, Snodgrass JW (2011) Salinization alters ecosystem structure in urban stormwater detention ponds. *Urban Ecosystems* 14: 723–736. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11252-011-0180-9>
- Vinarski MV (2017) The history of an invasion: phases of the explosive spread of the physid snail *Physella acuta* through Europe, Transcaucasia and Central Asia. *Biological Invasions* 19: 1299–1314. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-016-1339-3>
- Weiperth A, Bláha M, Szajbert B, Sepros R, Bányai Z, Patoka J, Kouba A (2020) Hungary: A European hotspot of non-native crayfish biodiversity. *Knowledge and Management of Aquatic Ecosystems* 421: 43. <https://doi.org/10.1051/kmae/2020035>

Supplementary material 1

Additional materials

Authors: James W. E. Dickey, Jonathan M. Jeschke, Gregor T. Steffen, Elžbieta Kazanavičiūtė, Reid S. Brennan, Elizabeta Briski

Data type: tables and figure (docx file)

Explanation note: table S1: Sample information downloaded from NCBI to allow us to validate the identification of our *A. helena* study organisms (“Our sample”). Known samples representing the four cryptic species (see Strong et al. 2017) as well as the closely related *Nassodonta dorri* and *Naytia granulosa* as an outgroup were used; table S2: First-order terms, FR parameters and associated significance levels resulting from logistic regression of proportional prey consumption across different prey densities at two experimental temperature treatments (22 °C and 18 °C) for the predator *Anentome helena* feeding on *Physella acuta* prey over 48 hours. The significant negative first-order term values under both temperature treatments indicate Type II functional responses (cf. Pritchard et al. 2017). Attack rate (a) and handling time (h) parameter estimates derived using Rogers’ random predator equation (Eq. 1), with p values obtained from the “frair_fit” function (Pritchard et al. 2017) indicative of estimate reliability. “***” $p < 0.01$. “*” $p < 0.05$; table S3: Comparisons of fitted coefficients using the delta or difference method of Juliano (2001) as provided by the frair package (Pritchard et al. 2017). Significant differences emboldened; table S4: Tukey post-hoc comparisons between total consumption of *Physella acuta* prey by *Anentome helena* across group size - temperature treatments; figure S1: Experimental water bath set-up featuring arenas (1 L plastic jars filled with 400 ml of water), air lines (drawn from a larger, orange tube), a heater and probe, and two circulation pumps to ensure uniform distribution of temperature, as demonstrated by photographs a) and b), and schematic c).

Copyright notice: This dataset is made available under the Open Database License (<http://opendata-commons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0/>). The Open Database License (ODbL) is a license agreement intended to allow users to freely share, modify, and use this Dataset while maintaining this same freedom for others, provided that the original source and author(s) are credited.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2023.18.2.103208.suppl1>